

PSYCHOSOCIAL ISSUE IN DRUG ABUSERS: A PSYCHOMETRIC APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Psychosocial challenges are prevalent in individuals struggling with substance abuse. The present study aims to develop a measure of Psycho-social issues of Drug Abusers by exploring the experience and manifestation in Pakistani culture. An open-ended interview approach was used to generate 33 items from 14 male participants aged 18-26 in the first phase of scale development. A pilot study was conducted on a sample of 10 male participants after content validation of a self-report measure of Psychosocial Issues. Furthermore, 150 male participants (18-26 years old, $M=22.62$; $SD=1.74$) were selected from government and private universities for psychometric testing of the Psycho-social Issue Scale (PIS) and Interpersonal Difficulty Scale. Based on the Promax Rotation Factor Analysis, the Psycho-social Issue Scale (PIS) is divided into two factors: Social Disruption and Personal Disruption. An analysis of the PIS indicated that it was internally consistent, construct valid, and reliable. Based on the Pakistani cultural context, findings are discussed in terms of factorial structure.

Keywords. Psycho-social issue, interpersonal problem. validity, reliability.

INTRODUCTION

University is the significant part of student life because they are introduced to new research and technology, and are encouraged to think creatively and independently. The university develops initiative and leadership skills that students can take with them throughout their lives, overcome intellectual challenges and achieve a sense of accomplishment through the university. This sudden transition causes many challenges for the students like having peer pressure, adjustment issues, indulge in dangerous activities like fighting, violence, self-harm, and getting into drugs, and become abusers (Millet, 2015). They believe they are using it for recreational purposes but it starts

affecting them in serious ways (Farhadinasab et al., 2008).

Drug abuse happens when someone misuses either licit or illicit drugs willfully for recreational, convenience, or perceived necessity reasons. Addiction often results from a more intensified and willful misuse of drugs (Zaman et al., 2015). The term 'drugs' refers to chemical substances, pharmaceutical preparations or natural substances that alter physiological, psychological, or biochemical processes (Weinberg et al., 2014). Drugs are classified into three categories according to its effects: stimulants, sedatives, or narcotics (Nelson, 2019). Drug abuse is a threatening issue in Pakistan and all over the world because almost 12 million are getting killed

by abusing or addicting to it and most representation are males (Ritchie & Roser, 2019; Zaman et al., 2015). A number of physical, psychological, social, and occupational problems are associated with substance abuse (alcohol, tobacco, and other drugs) (Hines & Lynskey, 2020). An individual's mental state is altered by psychoactive drugs, which affect the Central Nervous System (CNS) in various ways, causing health and behavioral problems (Daley, 2016). Suffering from severe substance abuse is considered to suffer from substance dependence, which has been recognized as a disorder (Grant et al., 2015). In addition to alcoholism, legal and illicit drugs can be abused (Bjork & Thomson, 2020). Abuse and dependence encompass a disorder within the meaning of the Code, such as a failure to fulfill major obligations at work, and persistent social, legal, and interpersonal problems related to the substance (Vajravelu et al., 2022).

The bio-Psycho-social model best explains the psycho-social issues of drug abuse (George Taukeni, 2019). It tells what psychological, social, and emotional factors contribute to an adult becoming a drug abuser or even a drug addict (Birtel et al., 2017). There are a number of health-related consequences associated with young adult substance abuse, including accidents, disabilities, and diseases (Donoghue et al., 2017). Suicide, homicide, accidents, and illness pose a disproportionate risk for youth who are addicted to alcohol or other drugs (Dunbar & Hockings, 2019). Youth who abuse substances are more likely to contract HIV/AIDS or other sexually transmitted diseases (Cordova et al., 2020). In the presence of mood-altering substances, poor judgment and impulse control may result in poor decision making and actions (Duessso, 2021).

A number of mental health problems in young adults are associated with substance abuse, including anxiety, depression, apathy, withdrawal, mood disturbance, conduct problems, personality disorders, and attempts to commit suicide (Blanco et al., 2016; Santana, 2018). Young adults who use marijuana have more difficulties with short-term memory, learning, and psycho-motor

skills (Dervaux, 2017). A person's motivation as well as their psycho-sexual and emotional development may also be influenced by their environment (Schwienteck & Banks, 2020). Adults who abuse drugs may be affected by a number of factors, whether they are internal or external (Volkow et al., 2018) like personal adversity, family crises, sometimes resulting in dysfunctional families (Thompson et al., 2013) and impacts both their siblings and parents (Schonfeld & Demaria, 2020). Object Relation Theory states that if the child in childhood is not properly taken care of by their parents they start to become dependent on other things like abusing drugs which are very life-endangering and impact families financially and emotionally (Comer, 2009). Due to poor family support and lack of communication adults feel more self-criticism and developed another psycho-social issue (Baetens et al., 2015). Early adults or late adults who have more psycho-social issues are more likely to become drug abusers as compared to those who have fewer psycho-social issues (Niaz et al., 2005) because it's a very sensitive and challenging period of life and they go through many hormonal changes, mood changes, and interpersonal problems. This is why they are being more vulnerable to get into substance use disorders (Mons et al., 2015).

Peers often alienate and stigmatize substance-abusing youth (Ifeoma et al., 2020). Alcohol and drug users are also less likely to participate in academics and community activities, denying their communities and peers positive contributions (Kanga, 2022). A strong correlation exists between these two behaviors and their consequences often include problems in school or at home, involvement in negative peer groups, a lack of neighborhood social controls, and violence (Sampson, 2017). In addition, gangs, drug trafficking, prostitution, youth homicides, and social and criminal justice concerns associated with substance abuse by adults (Ashraf, 2020). Adults who come from rural areas to urban areas are more inclined to be drug abusers (Tariq, 2017).

One of the alarming social problems in Pakistan is drug addiction, which is rapidly affecting a large portion of its population.

Approximately 8 million addicts live in the country, demonstrating the severity of this problem and Government and law enforcement agencies are already paying attention to drug addiction (Bhat & Imtiaz, 2017). Its prevalence is influenced by a number of social and psychological problems, including poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, anxiety, shame, guilt, a negative feedback loop, and loss of interest (Shah et al., 2020). Most users began abusing substances during their 15-18-year-old years due to peer influence, curiosity, and growing up. In addition to feeling good, socialization was a major reason for maintaining the behavior (Gopiram & Kishore, 2014). A lack of knowledge about alcohol and other drug abuse continues to be obscured by inaccurate perceptions and stereotypes. In addition to Asian heterogeneity and cultural barriers, substance abuse prevalence rates have also not been adequately studied. Moreover, taboos, denial, and a loss of face further obscure the extent of what is happening (Elkassam & Csiernik, 2020).

Give the significance of psycho-social issues of drug users in Pakistan, existing research and measurement tools are limited. (Poudel et al., 2016). A major aim of this study was to fill the gap in the literature by highlighting the psycho-social issues of drug abusers in Pakistan's culture through the identification of risk factors to escape from. It also aims to develop an indigenous scale for psycho-social issues of drug abusers in Pakistan's collectivistic culture for the purpose of developing a better understanding of the phenomenology, prevalence indicators, and manifestations of the disorder.

Method

The indigenous scale was developed by going through four main stages which include item generation, expert validation, pilot study, and psychometric properties.

Scale Development

Phase I: Item Generation

The first stage of scale development is exploring phenomenology. The aim of phenomenology was to gather the responses of the drug abusers about their psycho-social

problems. Before carrying out phenomenology, a question was conceptualized and asked from participants to get responses. The question that was formalized for the semi-structured interview was "What kind of problems/difficulties, do you think the people who use drugs experience in their daily lives?" For exploring phenomenology total of 14 participants approached with the age range of 18-26. There were 45 items but after several changes, and ambiguities, 44 items were finalized.

Phase II: Establishing Expert Validation

The aim of phase II was the expert validation stage. In this step, the items that were collated were presented to write here the number of experts for rating the items on the degree of their relevance to the desired construct. The experts rated each item on a 5-point rating scale, where 1 represents no relevance, while 5 indicates a great deal of relevance. The total numbers of items presented to the experts were 44, after incorporating their suggestions. Two of them were discarded. The final list consisted of 42 items.

Phase III: Pilot Study

Afterward, a pilot study was conducted. The aim of the pilot study was to test the user-friendliness of the scale and to identify the problems and ambiguities faced by participants while filling out the questionnaire. In a pilot study, 10 male participants were approached and were asked to fill the scale. The participant took an estimated 10 to 15 minutes while filling out the form. The questionnaire was finalized and was used in the main study for research purposes.

Phase IV: Psychometric Properties of Psycho-social Issues of Drug Abuse

The psychometric study of research is done to find an indigenous tool for the drug abuser. The total number of participants is 150. Male participants were selected to fill the questionnaire. Data collection was done from the students of BS1, BS2, BS3, and BS4. Their age ranges were from 18-26.

Participants

The research design was cross-sectional research and the snowball sampling technique was used. The setting of the data collection was a university setting. Participants' age range was from 18-26. They have recently graduated or are in the undergraduate program. Participants must have used drugs in the past 30 days otherwise they would be excluded.

Measures

Demographic Performa

The Performa consists of basic information like form number, age, gender, education, family system, number of family members, and brother and sister numbers.

Psychosocial Issue Scale of Drug Abuse (PISDA)

This indigenous tool was made for the psycho-social issues of drug abuse in University students. It had two factors which are Social Disruption and Personal Disruption. The scoring was done on the basis of a Likert scale consisting of 5 ratings. 1 (not at all), 2 (very less), 3 (sometimes), 4 (often), and 5 (always).

Interpersonal Difficulties Scale (IDS)

This scale was divided into 6 factors all the factors were based on the interpersonal problems faced by university students. The factors were dominant by others, low self-confidence, mistrust, lack of assertiveness, lack of boundaries, and instability in relationships. There were 61 items but, in this research, the short version of the scale has been used which consists of 31 items. The Likert scale was used for rating which starts

Figure 1

from 1 to 5. 1 (never), 2 (very less), 3 (sometimes), 4 (very much) and 5 (always) (Mahmood et al., 2014).

Procedure

In the procedure, the indigenous scale was given to drug abuse of the university population. There was a total of 150 participants who were taken from Government and private universities. They were first asked about their age and which semester they are currently enrolled in. Their age was more than they were not included. They were told they can ask anything if they have an issue with the questionnaire. Confidentiality will be kept.

Results

In the current research, Factor analysis was done on 42 total items of the indigenous scale of psycho-social problems of drug use in university students. Factor analysis was used which is exploratory factor analysis. Promax rotation was done several times. Firstly, it was done with four factors, then it was reduced to three, and lastly, it was done with two. Factor loading was also carried out two times firstly with .30 and .40 was carried out. KMO and Barlett's test was used. The result value of KMO is .861 and the score of Barlett is .000 which is highly significant. A Scree plot is used to see how many factors the scale retains. First, the scree plot was done with four factors, then with three factors, and at last with two factors to get a clear picture. Factor loading was done first with .30 and done to have a clear picture; it was done at .40 with Promax rotation.

Table 1: Factor Structure of 42 items of Psycho-social Issues of Drug Abuse with Pro-max Rotation

Sr. no.	Item No.	F1	F2
1	23	.47	.11
2	24	.55	.09
3	25	.57	.09
4	26	.46	.17
5	27	.58	.09
6	29	.47	.24
7	30	.44	.03
8	31	.58	-.01
9	32	.57	.04
10	33	.50	.20
11	34	.47	.01
12	36	.56	.16
13	37	.69	-.12
14	38	.62	-.02
15	39	.61	-.00
16	40	.54	.07
17	41	.62	.04
18	42	.44	.09
19	1	.08	.41
20	2	.21	.40
21	9	.14	.42
22	10	.14	.50
23	11	.08	.53
24	12	.05	.66
25	13	.10	.60
26	14	-.12	.54
27	15	-.00	.67
28	16	-.08	.75
29	17	.17	.45
30	18	-.03	.52
31	20	.01	.40
32	21	.11	.53
33	22	.19	.48

Eigen Values		10.51	2.84
% of Variance		24.78	6.77
% of Total Variance		8.93	8.41

Note. Items with .40 or above loadings are bolder in the corresponding factor, F1= Social Disruption, F2= Personal Disruption

Factor Description

Factor 1: Social Disruption

This factor contains 15 items. Social disruption means facing social issues or problems created by the family and the people they know. Drug abusers are faced highly with social-emotional issues. As seen by the responses recorded by the participants they bully them by calling them bad names. The statements in this factor underlined the stress about the availability of drugs, running away from people, being lazy, consuming

drugs, and getting away from friends. Relation to religion getting weaker.

Factor 2: Personal Disruption

This factor consisted of 18 items. Personal disruption which is unable to deal with themselves and poor self-esteem makes them more reliant on the use of drugs. As seen by the responses recorded was an Inability to engage with family. The items included less emphasis on studies and having more somatic problems like they are getting physically weak, numb, having sleep issues, and health-related concerns like heart palpitations getting high.

Reliability of Psycho-social Issue of Drug Abuse in University population

Table 2: Cronbach Alpha of the Psycho-social Issues of Drug Abuse

Factors	No. of Items	α
Social Disruption	18	.88
Personal Disruption	15	.85
Total Psychosocial Issues	33	.90

Note. α =Alpha Co-efficient

The above table showed that the Psycho-Social Issues Of Drug Abusers Scale (PIS) have high internal consistency or reliability.

Split-Half Reliability

PIS's split-half reliability was evaluated by using Odd-Even method. The scale was divided into two equal halves (odd items and even items). A significant correlation between the two halves ($r = .89$) was found.

Test Re-test Reliability

Test re-test reliability was established by giving the scale to participants two times in a duration of one week. Nine participants were given psycho-social forms. The correlation between psycho-social issues was ($r=.99$, $p<0.01$), reflects highly significant.

Concurrent Validity

The concurrent validity of the Psycho-social Issue Scale of Drug Abuse was checked with the established scale of Interpersonal Difficulty Scale (IDS) ($r=.55$ $p<0.01$).

Table 3: Inter-correlations, Means, and Standard Deviation of PIS and IDS

Factors	F1	F2	PIS Total	IDS Total
F1. Social Disruption	-	.53***	.91***	.48***
F2. Personal Disruption		-	.83***	.49***
PIS Total			-	.55***
IDS				-
M			96.63	85.81
SD			22.57	20.26

Note. PIS = Psycho-social Issues Scale=PIS, IDS = Interpersonal Difficulties Scale,

M=Mean and SD =Standard Deviation
* $p<.05$, ** $<.01$, *** $p<.001$.

Discussion

Psycho-social problems are thought to be problems that affect adolescents' behavior in college and have an impact on their mental and social functioning. They struggle with issues like anxiety, and depression in college students, as well as new concerns such mental disorders, antisocial conduct, traumatic events, and academic challenges and academic failure, etc. It has been also found it in the research which is done in western countries that the adolescents have been effected in higher percentage with psychosocial issues which leads them to drug abuse (Gebremariam et al., 2024). There was a research done on adolescents in which it can be seen that the psychosocial issues and having problems in college leads to greater use of drug abuse, In order to break free from stresses they start abusing drugs (Trucco, 2021). Family environment was an alarming sign of causing psycho-social issues in the children (Spiker et al., 2002; Degnan et al., 2010). The literature revealed that interpersonal problems lead to psychosocial issues like anxiety and depression (Wiseman et al., 2007). It Is been also found in the research, that people who are using drugs for a long time will have more self-criticism. Hence, it can be proved by the research done on people who use substances, that negative self-consciousness like guilt and shame are present in them, they consider themselves inferior to others (Batchelder et al., 2022).

In Pakistan, Drug addiction has increased at a very threatening rate. There are many developing factors seen in Pakistan which lead to the dependence on drugs. The late adolescence population has been highly affected by this endangering phenomenon (Ghazal, 2019). It has been seen that in University, students are being exposed to different situations and challenges in which they are been vulnerable to what is happening in the environment and forget the moral, and ethical values of society and family (Deressa & Azazh, 2011). Late adulthood is seen to have more life problems in their life as compared to early adolescents. This can be seen as in adolescence stage, they have the support of their families but in adulthood, all the help is taken away. They

have to be independent and do not ask their parents for help. It is also seen in the research that emerging adults abuse drugs and they are so much under pressure that they endanger their lives. Special preventive measures should be taken and some kind of organizations should be made in order to help these adult so they do not take dangerous measures (Wood et al., 2017).

There was no relevant psychosocial issue scale of drug abuse according to relevant to Pakistan Population. In the current study, the indigenous scale psycho-social issue was developed for the population of drug abuse in the university population. As there was no culturally reliable scale made in Pakistan according to our social norms, the current developed scale consists of 33 items. It included two main factors. First-factor Personal Disruption which regards the issue regarding oneself. The second factor is Social Disruption which means the issues caused by society and the outer environment. There was research done in Pakistan on the university population in which they have seen that when students come from college they do not only face academic difficulties but they are also faced with psychological issues like anxiety and depression (Rodgers & Tennison, 2009; Cooley et al., 2007; Tosevski et al., 2010; Zivin et al., 2009).

As a result, the goals of the current study are to provide the participants and said population with insight into the factors that contribute to the psychological problem of drug abuse, as is clear from the earlier research as well as the previous research that how psycho-social problems are leading to drug abuse. The results of the present study also showed that a large number of individuals have psychological problems as a result of their environmental stresses. Special preventive measures and counseling session should be made free for a better understanding of this alarming situation of drug abuse in Pakistan. The parents need to be educated with their children.

Limitations and Suggestions

Firstly, the limitations occurred due to the current Covid-19 situation. There was a restriction on entering some Universities and

collecting data from them which caused a hurdle in collecting the data. The data was collected from the male population instead of the female population. Future research can work on the female population, it would give a more generalized result. They can work on one drug and its psycho-social effect on the individual. This can help future researchers to work properly on the intervention plan for the drug abuser.

Conclusion

Drug abuse is considered to be a very alarming and endangering phenomenon that is fitly spreading all over the world. This population is considered to be a sensitive population and that is why the researchers look at the factors that made the individual the drug abuser. The research was done in order to make the scale reliable for the Pakistan population as there was no reliable scale made for the Pakistan university population. From the results, it was seen that the different demographics play a role in the psycho-social issues of a drug abuser.

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